

Deciphering Persian Music

A Systematic Approach Through Modal Classification and Synthesis (MCS)

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1. Introduction

1.1 The Modal Characteristics of Persian Music

Persian music, inherently improvisational, is rich in amorphous melodic figures that lend themselves to diverse combinations for improvisation, akin to the use of licks in jazz and popular music. These amorphous figures can either stand on their own or be woven together with others to craft larger structures, known as *gušeh*² in the realm of Persian musical tradition. Each figure is characterized by two main characteristics: rhythmic and modal. The focus of this study will be on the modal characteristics of these melodic figures. The modal characteristics within Persian music are delineated by two unique qualities, referred to as *maqām* and *māyeh*. As delineated in *Grove Music Online* (Lawergren 2001), these qualities are elucidated with reference to the previously discussed melodic figures in the following manner:

Persian classical music is represented by a corpus of amorphous pieces that are subject to extemporized renditions. They adhere to a modal principle that is defined by a set of pitches (*maqām*) and a certain melodic contour (*māyeh*). The pieces are collectively known as the *radif* ('row', 'line-up').

In this context, '*maqām*' is defined as a specific set of pitch classes that serve as the fundamental tonal framework for the formation of melodic structures. The exploration of *maqāms* in this research is based on a historical methodology grounded in the theoretical contributions of *Safī al-Dīn al-Urmawī*, a 13th-century Iranian music scholar, as presented in his work "*Kitāb-i Advār*"⁴ (The Book of Cycles). *Urmawī*'s theoretical framework illustrates the various potential divisions of the octave as segmented circles, which can be referred to as a kind of 'interval templates' (see picture on the right). From every degree of a circle, its modes are derived, each represented as a cycle⁵ emanating from the original circle. For instance, the Ionian and Dorian modes share identical interval patterns, thereby constituting distinct cycles within the same modal circle.

Each unique pitch class assignment to a specific circle (and not to a cycle) establishes a particular *maqām*, which in this sense can be considered a tone pool⁷. For instance, according to this definition, D Dorian and C Ionian share the same *maqām*, while D Dorian and C Dorian refer to different *maqāms*.

'*Māyeh*' denotes "a certain melodic contour" (Lawergren 2001) that emerges from the interplay of attraction and repulsion among the modal components. Subsequently, we will succinctly explore the modal components that are instrumental in shaping *māyeh*.

The Modal Forces Contributing to Māyeh Formation

● Anchor³

The 'anchor' is identified as a pitch within a *maqām*, which, even if momentarily, is cognitively established as the focal point of the respective modal entity ('home tone') or as a temporary point of stability. The identification of anchor as the initial tone delineates a cycle within the corresponding modal circle.

● Šāhed

The term '*šāhed*' refers to the note within a cycle that functions as the modal characteristic tone, distinguished by its pronounced emphasis through phenomenal accents and typically appearing more frequently than other tones.

● Modal Trichord

As mentioned, the key role in identifying the *šāhed* is played by the phenomenal accents on a pitch, particularly the pitch event. Adjacent to the *šāhed*, two additional tones are closely positioned, occupying the next levels of significance in this hierarchy. Together with the *šāhed*, these tones form what is termed in this paper the 'modal trichord'. By defining the configurations of the modal trichords, not only is the primary pitch range of a melodic figure ascertained, but also the shaping forces influencing the creation of melody are identified. For instance, when the *šāhed* is located in the middle of the trichord, the melodic movement tends towards convergence.

1.2 The Objective of the Theory

The primary objective of this research is to develop a comprehensive notational system that accurately represents amorphous melodic figures and their combinations, encapsulating the essential modal characteristics of Persian music. While the traditional *Radif* has served as a 'roadmap' for improvisation, providing models of melodic patterns and modulation, it does not encompass all potential musical conceptions that can arise from the diverse spectrum of amorphous modal figures within Persian music. The *Radif* presents fixed manifestations of melodies, which limit its flexibility and applicability for spontaneous improvisation and the broader modular structure of Persian music.

Therefore, this study aims to establish a more flexible foundational framework for improvisation, composition, and analysis that extends beyond the traditional *Radif*. By functioning similarly to how chord symbols in jazz provide a guide through modal concepts in both melodic and harmonic contexts, the proposed notational system seeks to offer a versatile tool that can better facilitate communication among musicians across various settings and embrace the full range of modal expressions in Persian music.

Research Question

The central research question guiding this study is:

How can a notational system be devised that effectively represents amorphous melodic figures and their combinations, accurately reflects the essential modal properties of Persian music, and enables the recognition of similar structures, while serving as an informational framework for communication among musicians in improvisation, composition, and pedagogical contexts?

This question aims to address the limitations of the *Radif* in its traditional role and to explore a systematic approach to notating the fluid modal structures in Persian music, bridging the gap between traditional forms of representation and the need for a versatile, communicative tool for performance, composition, and education.

1.3 The Microtones in Persian Music

In addition to the sharp (#) and flat (b) symbols, Persian music employs two unique microtonal accidentals: '*sori*', for raising the pitch, and '*koron*', for lowering it. The microtones in Persian music diverge from an equal temperament, with the alterations caused by *sori* and *koron* extending beyond 50 cents. However, this study will not delve into intonation specifics but rather focus on representing the pitch space of Persian music and within this framework, microtonal accidentals are represented by half-sharp (‡) and half-flat (d) symbols. As is the case in this study, models that employ the concept of equidistant tone grids to illustrate the pitch space of Persian music are also prevalent in ancient theoretical works, such as *Urmawī*'s book. In these works, the interval lying between the major and minor second, is uniformly called '*mojannab*'⁶, even though it signifies two unequal sub-intervals within the minor third in practical use. For instance, in the figure on the left, *Urmawī* labels both the interval between the notes 'د' (equivalent to D) and 'و' (equivalent to E^d) as well as the interval between 'و' (E^d) and 'ج' (equivalent to F) as 'جـ' (Mojannab).

Utilizing the previously described accidentals, four specific types of the second interval, integral to Persian music, are defined:

- The 'minor second'⁷, also known as a 'half-tone', marked as '**H**' in this study, represents the smallest interval (e.g. D-E^b).
- The 'neutral tone'⁸, marked as '**N**' in this study, has a size that falls between the minor and major second (e.g. D-E^d).
- The 'major second'⁹, or 'whole-tone', marked as '**W**' in this study, is the well-established interval used in Western music (e.g. D-E).
- The 'plus tone'¹⁰, marked as '**P**' in this study, spans a size between the major second and the augmented second (e.g. D^d-E).

2. Foundations of the Proposed Theoretical Model

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2-1. Encoding the Modal Notations of the Melodic Figures ($X_n^{\wedge}my$)

This research aims to methodically investigate the modal characteristics of prevalent melodic figures that constitute the core elements in Persian music. The intent is to synthesize the vast spectrum of Persian musical corpus by focusing on their modal dimension. To this end, each figure is encoded as $X_n^{\wedge}my$, a notation that succinctly encapsulates their fundamental modal qualities.

X: MODAL CIRCLE

The designation 'X' indicates the specific modal circle associated with the melodic figure.

X_n : CYCLE

In the schematic notation $X_n^{\wedge}my$, the placeholder 'n' specifies the anchor tone degree within the relevant modal circle, thereby establishing a cycle denoted as 'Xn'.

$\wedge m$: ŠĀHED POSITION

The position of the *šāhed*, denoted by the variable ' $\wedge m$ ' as a generic degree number in the schematic notation $X_n^{\wedge}my$, signifies its placement within the cycle 'Xn' in relation to the anchor tone.

y: MELODIC MODEL

In the schematic notation $X_n^{\wedge}my$, the lowercase 'y' denotes the configuration of the trichord and the position of the *šāhed* tone within it, which can manifest in the following ways:

- a (•••):**
The modal trichord consists of three adjacent tones, with *šāhed* being the first or lowest tone.
- b (•••):**
The modal trichord consists of three adjacent tones, with *šāhed* being the middle tone.
- c (•••):**
The modal trichord consists of three adjacent tones, with *šāhed* being the last or highest tone.
- e (•x•):**
The modal trichord consists of three non-adjacent tones chosen from a sequence of four contiguous tones within the cycle, with the *šāhed* being the second highest tone. The excluded tone is located between the two lower tones of the trichord.
- f (••x•):**
The modal trichord consists of three non-adjacent tones chosen from a sequence of four contiguous tones within the cycle, with the *šāhed* serving as the highest tone and the excluded tone being its lower adjacent one.

$\wedge my$: MĀYEH

The compound notation ' $\wedge my$ ' in the schematic code signifies the relative positioning of key modal elements within a melodic figure, particularly the *šāhed*, trichord, and anchor tone. It is through the interactions of attraction and repulsion among these elements that the melodic contour, referred to as *māyeh*, is established.

SUMMARY

This diagram summarizes all the components of the modal notations for melodic figures and presents the corresponding annotations, as follows:

- Maqām
- Melodic Figure
- Circle
- Cycle
- Māyeh
- Melodic Model

2-2. Overview of Circles and Cycles (X_n)

This section presents the modal circles used in the corpus of Persian music, along with their associated cycles. It features segmented circles that illustrate the octave's division within each modal circle, with a clockwise direction indicating the cycles. Additionally, the interval pattern for each cycle is identified, starting from its anchor tone, denoted by the number '1', through the chromatically precise use of Arabic numerals. Numerals without accidentals signify major or perfect intervals, while the inclusion of accidentals modifies these intervals, either enlarging or diminishing them as required.

R₁	1	2	d ₃	4	5	d ₆	b ₇
R₂	1	d ₂	b ₃	4	d ₅	b ₆	b ₇
R₃	1	d ₂	d ₃	4	d ₅	d ₆	d ₇
R₄	1	2	d ₃	4	5	6	d ₇
R₅	1	d ₂	b ₃	4	5	d ₆	b ₇
R₆	1	d ₂	d ₃	‡ ₄	5	d ₆	d ₇
R₇	1	2	3	‡ ₄	5	6	d ₇
Q₁	1	2	d ₃	4	5	6	b ₇
Q₂	1	d ₂	b ₃	4	5	b ₆	b ₇
Q₃	1	d ₂	d ₃	‡ ₄	d ₅	d ₆	d ₇
Q₄	1	2	3	4	5	6	d ₇
Q₅	1	2	b ₃	4	5	d ₆	b ₇
Q₆	1	d ₂	d ₃	4	d ₅	b ₆	b ₇
Q₇	1	2	3	‡ ₄	5	6	7
O₁	1	2	b ₃	4	5	6	b ₇
O₂	1	b ₂	b ₃	4	5	b ₆	b ₇
O₃	1	2	3	# ₄	5	6	7
O₄	1	2	3	4	5	6	b ₇
O₅	1	2	b ₃	4	5	b ₆	b ₇
O₆	1	b ₂	b ₃	4	b ₅	b ₆	b ₇
O₇	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
S₁	1	2	b ₃	4	5	6	7
S₂	1	b ₂	b ₃	4	5	6	b ₇
S₃	1	2	3	# ₄	# ₅	6	7
S₄	1	2	3	# ₄	5	6	b ₇
S₅	1	2	3	4	5	b ₆	b ₇
S₆	1	2	b ₃	4	b ₅	b ₆	b ₇
S₇	1	b ₂	b ₃	b ₄	b ₅	b ₆	b ₇
H₁	1	2	d ₃	4	5	d ₆	7
H₂	1	d ₂	b ₃	4	d ₅	6	b ₇
H₃	1	d ₂	d ₃	4	‡ ₅	d ₆	d ₇
H₄	1	2	d ₃	# ₄	5	6	d ₇
H₅	1	d ₂	3	4	5	d ₆	b ₇
H₆	1	‡ ₂	d ₃	‡ ₄	5	d ₆	d ₇
H₇	1	b ₂	b ₃	d ₄	b ₅	b ₆	db ₇
B₁	1	2	3	‡ ₄	‡ ₅	6	7
B₂	1	2	d ₃	‡ ₄	5	6	b ₇
B₃	1	d ₂	d ₃	4	5	b ₆	b ₇
B₄	1	2	d ₃	‡ ₄	d ₅	d ₆	d ₇
B₅	1	d ₂	d ₃	d ₄	d ₅	d ₆	b ₇
B₆	1	2	b ₃	4	5	d ₆	d ₇
B₇	1	b ₂	b ₃	4	d ₅	b ₆	b ₇
C₁	1	d ₂	3	4	5	d ₆	7
C₂	1	‡ ₂	d ₃	‡ ₄	5	‡ ₆	d ₇
C₃	1	b ₂	b ₃	d ₄	5	b ₆	db ₇
C₄	1	2	d ₃	# ₄	5	d ₆	7
C₅	1	d ₂	3	4	d ₅	6	b ₇
C₆	1	‡ ₂	d ₃	4	‡ ₅	d ₆	d ₇
C₇	1	b ₂	db ₃	4	b ₅	b ₆	db ₇
X₁	1	d ₂	3	4	d ₅	d ₆	7
X₂	1	‡ ₂	d ₃	4	5	‡ ₆	d ₇
X₃	1	b ₂	db ₃	d ₄	5	b ₆	db ₇
X₄	1	d ₂	d ₃	# ₄	5	d ₆	7
X₅	1	2	‡ ₃	‡ ₄	5	‡ ₆	d ₇
X₆	1	‡ ₂	d ₃	4	‡ ₅	d ₆	b ₇
X₇	1	b ₂	db ₃	4	d ₅	b ₆	db ₇
K₁	1	d ₂	d ₃	4	5	d ₆	d ₇
K₂	1	2	d ₃	‡ ₄	5	6	d ₇
K₃	1	d ₂	d ₃	4	5	d ₆	b ₇
K₄	1	2	d ₃	‡ ₄	5	d ₆	d ₇
K₅	1	d ₂	d ₃	4	d ₅	d ₆	b ₇
K₆	1	2	d ₃	4	5	d ₆	d ₇
K₇	1	d ₂	b ₃	4	d ₅	d ₆	b ₇
T₁	1	d ₂	3	4	5	b ₆	b ₇
T₂	1	‡ ₂	d ₃	‡ ₄	d ₅	d ₆	d ₇
T₃	1	b ₂	b ₃	b ₄	b ₅	b ₆	db ₇
T₄	1	2	b ₃	4	5	d ₆	7
T₅	1	b ₂	b ₃	4	d ₅	6	b ₇
T₆	1	2	3	‡ ₄	# ₅	6	7
T₇	1	2	d ₃	# ₄	5	6	b ₇

3. Depiction of the Radif Repertoire as Case Study

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In Persian music, distinct modal entities known as 'guṣeh' emerge from individual melodic figures or their modular compositions, which vary in māyeh, maqām, or both. Each guṣeh possesses unique characteristics, whether modal, rhythmic, or both, and together, they constitute the larger modal categories known as 'dastgāh's, the overarching framework of the Persian musical tradition. A certain manifestation of all dastgāhs and guṣehs, which serves as a model for the presentation of Persian music and as a roadmap for improvisation, is called Radif. This study draws upon Nur-Alli Borumand's rendition of the Radif (Tala'i 2015) as the primary reference for the corpus of melodic structures in Persian music under investigation.

3-1. Compendium of Modal Notations for Identified Melodic Figures

This section provides a sample inventory of modal notations for approximately 100 of the roughly 220 amorphous melodic figures identified within the Radif. These figures are essential for the modular architecture of larger structures, namely guṣeh within the overarching modal system 'dastgāh'. The list is organized in a manner commonly described as 'light to dark' in jazz theory when discussing the presentation of modes, exemplified by the spectrum from 'Lydian to Locrian'. An earlier appearance of a modal cycle on the list indicates that larger intervals are positioned lower. Beside each modal notation, an audio example is provided. In every audio example, the note 'C' is initially established as the anchor tone, followed by the introduction of the respective 'māyeh', which illustrates the 'šāhed' in relation to the corresponding trichord. Subsequently, the 'maqām' (the tone pool) is demonstrated through a scale-like presentation of the relevant tone assignment for the particular modal cycle.

ID. Modal Notation	Audio Example	ID. Modal Notation	Audio Example
1. H ₆ [^] 1c		51. Q ₁ [^] 1c	
2. T ₂ [^] 3a		52. Q ₁ [^] 2b	
3. T ₂ [^] 3b		53. Q ₁ [^] 3a	
4. T ₂ [^] 3c		54. Q ₁ [^] 3b	
5. T ₂ [^] 4b		55. Q ₁ [^] 3c	
6. T ₂ [^] 4c		56. Q ₁ [^] 3e	
7. T ₂ [^] 5c		57. Q ₁ [^] 4b	
8. C ₆ [^] 1b		58. Q ₁ [^] 4c	
9. C ₆ [^] 3b		59. Q ₁ [^] 5b	
10. C ₆ [^] 3f		60. Q ₁ [^] 5c	
11. X ₂ [^] 3b		61. K ₆ [^] 1c	
12. R ₇ [^] 1b		62. K ₆ [^] 3a	
13. O ₇ [^] 1a		63. K ₆ [^] 3b	
14. O ₇ [^] 1b		64. R ₁ [^] 1a	
15. O ₇ [^] 1c		65. R ₁ [^] 1c	
16. O ₇ [^] 2a		66. R ₁ [^] 2a	
17. O ₇ [^] 2b		67. R ₁ [^] 2b	
18. O ₇ [^] 3b		68. R ₁ [^] 3b	
19. O ₇ [^] 3c		69. R ₁ [^] 4b	
20. O ₇ [^] 4b		70. R ₁ [^] 4c	
21. O ₇ [^] 4c		71. R ₁ [^] 5a	
22. O ₇ [^] 5c		72. R ₁ [^] 5b	
23. Q ₄ [^] 1a		73. S ₁ [^] 1a	
24. Q ₄ [^] 1b		74. S ₁ [^] 1b	
25. Q ₄ [^] 1c		75. S ₁ [^] 2b	
26.		76.	

A visual comparison video between two melodic figures of the same 'māyeh' (namely 4b), each referring to a different modal circle.

3-2. Constructing Composite Modal Frameworks

This section delineates the composition of amorphous figures as modal blocks for constructing larger modal structures, specifying the intervals between their anchor tones. These intervals are precisely denoted through the use of Roman numerals, applied chromatically exact, and are referenced in relation to the anchor tone of the primary guṣeh within the respective dastgāh, known as 'darāmad'. In this paper, we refer to this primary anchor tone as 'finalis' and denote it with the Roman numeral 'I'. The notation 'III-R₄[^]2b' indicates, for example, that the building block 'R₄[^]2b' is constructed a 'minor third' (denoted by 'III') above the finalis in darāmad. Numerals without accidentals signify major or perfect intervals, while the inclusion of accidentals modifies these intervals, either enlarging or diminishing them as required. Notations marked with the same color represent blocks that share the same maqām (tone pool).

The corresponding audio recording of Nur-ali Borumand's original interpretation of Mirza Abdollah's Radif.

Block	Dastgāh	Guṣeh	Modal Notation
1	Māhur	Darāmad-e Māhur	I-O7 [^] 1b
2	Māhur	Kerešmeh (Māhur) Block 1	I-O7 [^] 1c
3	Māhur	Kerešmeh (Māhur) Block 2	I-O7 [^] 3a
4	Māhur	Kerešmeh (Māhur) Block 3	I-O7 [^] 2b
5	Māhur	Āvāz Block 1	II-O1 [^] 1a
6	Māhur	Āvāz Block 2	I-O7 [^] 1a
7	Māhur	Āvāz Block 3	II-O1 [^] 1a
8	Māhur	Āvāz Block 4	I-O7 [^] 1b
9	Māhur	Moqaddameh Dād Block 1	II-O1 [^] 3b
10	Māhur	Moqaddameh Dād Block 2	I-O7 [^] 1a
11	Māhur	Dād Block 1	I-O7 [^] 2a
12	Māhur	Dād Block 2	II-O1 [^] 3b
13	Māhur	Majles Afruz (Māhur) Block 1	II-O1 [^] 3b
14	Māhur	Majles Afruz (Māhur) Block 2	II-O1 [^] 1a
15	Māhur	Majles Afruz (Māhur) Block 3	I-O7 [^] 1b
16	Māhur	Majles Afruz (Māhur) Block 4	III-O5 [^] 3c
17	Māhur	Majles Afruz (Māhur) Block 5	I-O7 [^] 1b
18	Māhur	Xosravāni (Māhur) Block 1	I-O7 [^] 4b
19	Māhur	Xosravāni (Māhur) Block 2	II-O5 [^] 4b
20	Māhur	Xosravāni (Māhur) Block 3	I-O7 [^] 3b
21	Māhur	Xosravāni (Māhur) Block 4	I-O7 [^] 1b
22	Māhur	Delkaš Block 1	I-R1 [^] 5a
23	Māhur	Delkaš Block 2	V-R5 [^] 1a
24	Māhur	Delkaš Block 3	IV-R4 [^] 2b
25	Māhur	Delkaš Block 4	IV-H1 [^] 2b
26	Māhur	Čahārmezrāb va Forud-e Delkaš Block 1	V-R5 [^] 1b
27	Māhur	Čahārmezrāb va Forud-e Delkaš Block 2	V-R5 [^] 1a
28	Māhur	Čahārmezrāb va Forud-e Delkaš Block 3	II-O5 [^] 4b
29	Māhur	Čahārmezrāb va Forud-e Delkaš Block 4	II-O1 [^] 2a
30	Māhur	Čahārmezrāb va Forud-e Delkaš Block 5	III-O5 [^] 3c
31	Māhur	Čahārmezrāb va Forud-e Delkaš Block 6	I-O7 [^] 1b
32	Māhur	Yāvarān Block 1	IV-O7 [^] 2a

Constructing Composite Modal Frameworks: An Illustrative Example

Mohayyer in Māhur

The diamond-shaped note head represents the anchor tone of the respective block. The plus symbol indicates the šāhed-note, and trichords are depicted by eighth-note beams.